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SAPEA Expert Workshop Report
Advanced Materials

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Advanced Materials

SAPEA Expert Workshop Report

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Summary

The expert workshop is a vital part of SAPEA's evidence review process. It provides a critique of the draft SAPEA evidence review report (ERR) by the wider expert community.

The workshop on advanced materials was held on 22 September 2025 in Brussels as a hybrid meeting. Participants included the invited experts, members of the working group, SAPEA representatives, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, and staff of the European Commission.

The workshop format was as follows:

- After a general introduction to the evidence review report, a keynote speaker presented an overall assessment of the report, with initial observations on strengths, possible limitations, and gaps.
- Each of the main sections was then introduced, followed by feedback from invited discussants and an opportunity for open discussion.

After the workshop, members of the working group considered the feedback and agreed on the actions that should be taken to address it. The draft evidence review report was then revised, prior to undergoing formal peer review. The final version has been published as a SAPEA evidence review report and is available on the SAM website¹.

1 <https://scientificadvice.eu/advice/advanced-materials/>

Introduction

SAPEA's expert workshop is a vital part of the evidence review process.

It fulfils the following purposes:

- Providing a critique of the draft SAPEA evidence review report by the wider expert community: Invited experts to the workshop give informal feedback, offering constructive input to the working group that is producing the report.
- Developing further the conclusions and evidence-based policy options in the evidence review report.

Experts attend and give their views in a personal capacity and not as representatives of their employer or any other organisation with which they are associated. Chatham House rules² are observed, with no attribution to any individual.

This workshop was conducted in a hybrid mode, both in Brussels and remotely. A list of attendees is given in Annex 1: List of attendees to this report.

2 More information at <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule>

Context and scope

The [Scientific Advice Mechanism](#) (SAM) provides independent scientific evidence and policy recommendations to the European institutions, by request of the College of Commissioners. The [scoping paper](#) for advanced materials sets out the formal request for advice from the College of European Commissioners to the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors. Within this context, the European Commission asked SAPEA to produce by January 2026 an evidence review report with policy options to support the work of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors in answering the two questions in the scoping paper:

■ 1. What contribution can advanced materials bring to EU's strategic autonomy?

This should cover:

- ▶ Research areas in advanced materials reflecting EU core strengths, and with highest potential impact on industrial competitiveness and gaps where the EU should put additional efforts, and
- ▶ Cross-cutting research challenges on safe and sustainable advanced materials for the circular economy (design, development, characterisation, processing, production, and product integration).

The Group should identify best practices, pitfalls, and roadblocks to avoid.

■ 2. How can the cross-fertilisation of innovation in advanced materials be enhanced?

This should cover:

- ▶ Identifying mechanisms to tap the potential of new innovative functionalities across sectors and applications, and to stimulate new business models and innovation markets, and
- ▶ Facilitating alignment and feedback loops between basic research and industrial needs for advanced materials, and supporting uptake by industry.

The Group should identify best practices, pitfalls, and roadblocks to avoid.

The [evidence review report](#) by SAPEA synthesises the evidence, in response to these questions. As requested, all advice should remain within the scope of the [Commission Communication on Advanced Materials for Industrial Leadership](#)—mobility, energy, construction, electronics and cross-cutting aspects—and also include health.

Report of the workshop

A summary of each session is given below, followed by a summary of the overall suggestions for improvement to the draft report at the end of each session. We present the sessions according to the sequence of the chapters in the draft report at the time, although the workshop itself did not follow this sequence and the chapter numbering changed in the final version. The figures and tables numbering also changed in the final version. The programme for the workshop is set out in Annex 2: Programme and reflects the sequence and numbering followed in the draft at the time of the workshop.

Welcome and introduction to SAPEA

All participants were warmly welcomed. They included invited experts, members of the SAPEA working group, representatives of SAPEA, members of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (GCSA) and staff of the European Commission (see Annex 1: List of attendees). The role of SAPEA was then outlined (see the Context and scope section). Finally, the purpose of the expert workshop and basic ground rules were clarified (see the Introduction section in this report). Appreciation was shown for the time and effort given by the experts to think about the future of materials.

Introduction to the Scientific Advice Mechanism and the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, and background to the request

The scoping questions were introduced and background for the need for this evidence review report on advanced materials was provided (see [scoping paper](#)). The SAPEA working group of experts was formed within this setting. In addition, an *Industry and innovation workshop* was held online on June 4, 2025, to support the evidence-gathering process for the second scoping question.

In addition to the five sectors of focus set up by the Technology Council on Advanced Materials—energy, mobility, construction, electronics, and health—an emphasis on digitalisation, artificial intelligence (AI), and the circular economy, was also requested, due to their importance to the European Commission.

The ERR and the Scientific Opinion, drafted respectively by the SAPEA working group and by the GCSA, will be handed over to the Commissioner for Research and Innovation and will directly inform the Advanced Materials Act, whose publication is foreseen in 2026.

Overview of the SAPEA evidence review report on advanced materials

The co-chair of the working group provided a summary of the evidence review report draft. The report includes an introduction chapter followed by individual chapters on sustainability; digitalisation, data, simulation, and AI; manufacturing; legislation; basic research; and conclusions.

The presentation focused two main points: the definition of and need for advanced materials, along with some examples presented in the report; and some of the sectors of activity and cross-sectoral topics highlighted in the report.

Definition of and the need for advanced materials, examples

Regarding the definition of advanced materials, the OECD specifies advanced materials as specific materials with improved or innovative performances or a substitute for harmful or critical materials. Materials have always transformed humankind and societies, going back to the Bronze Age and Roman times. One of the critical hallmarks of advanced materials, however, is that they are expected to be disruptive. Materials often derive from either sporadic, individual scientific findings, or from years of persistent research. Overall, they need systematic research and innovation to allow this disruption.

Currently, many different types of advanced materials exist, such as two-dimensional nanomaterials; nanoparticles; different types of liquid crystals, important for devices in various aspects; gels used in biomedicine; ceramics for electronics and construction; coatings; bio-derived materials, such as plant-derived materials; functional proteins; DNA used for nanoconstruction and different applications; viral capsids used for vaccinations; quantum materials, a strongly emerging group used for example for sensing and especially in quantum computers; electroactive polymers; inorganic nanomaterials; and metal alloys. Other examples include emerging technologies such as AI and machine learning (ML), which deal with data-driven materials or approaches; multi-scale simulation, a very complex example that implies understanding from the nanoscale up to the macroscopic scale, and requires handling an immense amount of data; or synthetic biology, dealing specifically with materials' properties to achieve functions; circular manufacturing, among others.

Emerging needs for advanced materials include sustainability, re-circulation, resource efficiency, avoiding short usage, renewable natural resources, and green technologies. Other needs relate to economic, geopolitical, and societal constraints, and ML, AI, digitalisation, and synthetic biology.

In the report, some specificities of a future definition of advanced materials are provided that will help distinguish them from mainstream (conventional) materials. First, emerging advanced materials are typically multi-component with many interactions. To master complexity, they exploit massive amounts of data and information. First, the data-driven analysis of their properties could be highly valuable. For example, AI and ML can help predict protein folding, which has been almost impossible to understand. Rather than providing understanding, these techniques allow researchers to master complexity. Second, upcoming data-driven laboratories are accelerating experimental work at scale, powered by massive

parallel data-driven synthesis protocols. Third, data-driven approaches are often combined with simulations to access artificial data when enough data are not available. Finally, and equally or even more important, all biological materials have information in their structure, as they have a certain order in their chemistries, and this information is core to allow their assembly for functional systems. These four aspects will certainly be in the core of the next advanced materials.

Sectors

The working group considered several sectors in the report. First, it features advanced materials related to energy production, storage, management, and efficiency. Europe is not robust in energy compared to China, for example, which leads in various forms of energy such as batteries. Europe needs therefore to be extremely selective to win in the energy field. Other points considered in the report regarding this sector include materials for clean and renewable energy; hydrogen storage, transport, and production; electrochemical converters; magnets; thermoelectrics, catalysts and photovoltaics, and batteries; materials for CO₂ capture and valorisation; solar and wind energy converters; wind turbine blades and generators; and thermal (passive) engineering.

The electronics sector is also featured in the report. Europe is strong in this area due to its robust research environments. The report also identifies that sustainable and high-performance materials for data centres are needed due to their high-energy consumption, and highlights the need to reduce electronic waste in Europe. One aspect that is particularly emphasised and that Europe is strong in is quantum and neuromorphic materials. Other points include alternatives to silicon; recyclable and biodegradable materials; rare metal resource efficiency; next-generation semiconductors; flexible and printed electronics; and additive manufacturing.

Construction impacts other priority areas, for example, carbon footprint, and is therefore relevant to address. This sector also relates to transportation, which needs high-strength and low-weight materials where different types of composites are relevant. Care is advised, because lightweight, strong composites are developed all over the world, so addressing European-specific strengths is needed. In particular, China's efforts in composites are considerable.

In the health and biomedical sector, the report highlights how there are several efforts related to viral capsids and nuclear capsids in Europe. Other aspects include: the need for qualification and lifetime prediction; multi-functional materials for regenerative medicine, tissue engineering, cell therapy, drug delivery, and biosensing; implants and devices, such as antibacterial surfaces and ergonomic customisation; recycling of biocompatible materials for implants and devices; and digital technologies, such as bioimprinting, and quantum dots in theragnostic, biosensing, and bioimaging.

Cross-sectoral topics

The report is organised around several cross-sectoral topics. Among them, data-driven and simulation-based advanced materials are featured, namely: data-driven automated laboratories for experimental approaches, and data- and simulation-driven materials design and discovery, and the need for high quality databases.

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Sustainability is an area with an emerging need for advanced materials, and it is used as an umbrella term in the report and discussed in depth. Sustainability relates not only to reducing carbon footprints, but several different aspects covered in life-cycle analysis, including: the use of renewable resources and energy; controlled life cycles with waste recycling; reducing greenhouse gas emissions; preventing waste; minimising environmental hazards and toxicity; promoting safety; maximising the content of raw materials in products and ensuring resource effectiveness; reducing organic solvents; high energy efficiency and clean and lean production processes; and use of life cycle assessment (LCA). Other aspects discussed encompass raw materials sourcing and the need for sustainability; the life-cycle perspective; different forms of sustainability (green chemistry, economic sustainability, social sustainability, and the concept of safe and sustainable by design); strategies for circularity; and synthetic biology, one of the core fields for green production. All these aspects are relevant in the European context and should be considered when suggesting policy options and discussing sustainability. Therefore, the need for evidence-based regulations, not over-regulation, is emphasised.

As a conclusion, a general reflection about the status of the report was made. Some aspects still need improvement, especially the policy options chapter, which misses a discussion on how to differentiate Europe from other countries like China. In addition, some material classes are still missing from the report, such as fluorinated materials, metal clusters, metamaterials, topological materials, and dissipative materials that will become available in future. References are also incomplete, and figures will be added.

Keynote

Summary of the keynote presentation

An invited keynote provided an overall assessment of the report, discussing strengths, possible limitations, and gaps, along with recommendations to improve the report.

Strengths of the report

The report demonstrates clear relevance toward EU policy, particularly for important acts—the Green Deal, the Critical Raw Materials Act, and the Circular Economy Action Plan—thus directly satisfying the request from the Commission. The report also proposes a series of useful concrete policy options, featuring the following important points: the notion of digital product passports; the investment in AI and database development; regulatory sandboxes, where companies could try things without being at risk of losing too much, along with modular scale-up infrastructures; and circularity measures and incentives.

A comprehensive coverage from raw materials sourcing to the end-of-life is also offered, including sustainability, digitalisation, manufacturing, governance, and research. The holistic view of sustainability frameworks provided is also considered a strength. In addition to LCA, the report includes additional qualitative assessments, such as safe and sustainable by design (SSbD), and the need for multi-criteria decision analysis. The report rightly articulates a forward-looking perspective by highlighting emerging technologies, such as AI-driven design, bio-based systems, synthetic biology, high-temperature materials, MXenes, and others. Finally, the basic research and innovation aspects are covered as well.

Limitations and gaps

While the report presents a range of materials and technologies, it does not precisely define advanced materials. In addition, all materials are presented with equal importance, even though some of them are trivial and others high-risk, high-gain futuristic materials. Instead, these materials and technologies could be ranked based on the EU position in relation to the international competition, their potential societal and economic impact, and their degree of maturity. As a third point, many important materials are not discussed in the report. These include materials for nuclear technology (only high-temperature systems are discussed); metamaterials; engineered living materials; material interfaces with biological entities; precision polymers; dynamic networks; materials for photonics; and textiles. Finally, some technologies, such as process intensification, are also not mentioned.

Recommendations

Several propositions were then put forward that could improve the report. First, add a table of the materials and systems discussed in the report, including a few possible missing items, and rank them according to their level of maturity related to the scientific and technological dimensions, and the transfer towards industry and market. Give a rationale for why they are considered advanced and discuss risks and gains associated with them.

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Second, while the Commission asked for a material agnostic position in the scoping paper, this is not a useful approach for organic and inorganic material categories, which are dealt with in an identical manner in the ERR. The human body is made of hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, iron, copper, and others, mostly elements below the atomic number (Z) twenty. Nature uses organic materials that are atom-economic and sustainable, but generally not very efficient. On the contrary, the elements used by humankind are very diverse. While humans extract everything from the Earth's crust using less sustainable means, the systems they create remain very efficient. Therefore, organic and inorganic materials should be treated differently. The report discusses synthetic biology, which does not apply to inorganic materials, and bio-sourcing, only applicable to organic materials. The structure and dynamics of organic materials are generally very complex compared to inorganics, which makes their numerical simulations/twins much less effective and the massive use of AI and ML tools for them even a more remote possibility. Organic materials often cannot compete with inorganic materials for applications, as they are often less efficient. Given the critical differences, discussing a global view on materials while making a distinction between organic and inorganic materials and technologies will be useful.

The third proposition regards data. As rightly pointed out, curated high-quality data are imperative for LCA, SSbD, AI, and ML applications. The report does not specify, however, how to obtain such curated databases. This is considered a daunting task; given the complexity of materials, the intertwining of processing, structure, and function of materials, the metadata for any given material is enormous. To address this challenge, three suggestions are made. First, consider the trust aspect along with FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) practices to make databases tamper-proof. Secondly, based on this trusted data, the EU can elaborate on trusted norms and standards for databases to avoid problems that may be plaguing US databases in the current political context. Such standardisation practices will give the EU a unique advantage over its competitors. Lastly, incorporate short-, mid-, and long-term strategies for developing such databases, namely through the concept of EU-based trusted data foundries.

Fourth, challenges associated with training and education are not addressed in the report. Well-trained people are key to success in advanced materials. It is necessary to incorporate sustainability, AI/ML, innovation, and advanced material science in education curricula. For example, FAMEAIS (Functional Advanced Materials Engineering with Artificial Intelligence for Sustainability) is an Erasmus Mundus master's degree programme training individuals in these important topics. In this context, it is important to understand what policies/levers the EU has to favour the emergence of such master's degrees, and how to educate engineers and scientists who are not redundant with AI. An option could be to create an EU alliance of master's degrees in materials science and engineering with financial support from the EU and industry. These programmes should include sustainability, innovation and AI/ML in their curriculum and share educational resources such as MOOCs (massive open online courses), blended mobility, or student competitions to create a new workforce that can address challenges in advanced materials.

The report does not discuss possible conflicting goals regarding societal acceptance of new technologies. For instance, does Europe need robust or efficient materials? Should it prioritise geo-

strategy or environmental protection first? Should Europe care about social sustainability or industrial redevelopment? Maybe all this can be done, but prioritisation is needed, and the report needs to address these questions.

Finally, circularity and synthetic biology offer opportunities, but they also entail costs. It remains challenging to develop an economically sustainable circular life cycle for advanced materials. For example, in polymers, virgin resins are of better quality and less expensive than recycled resins; hence, even if externalities were included, recycled resins are still less desirable. On the other hand, synthetic biology uses large amounts of fluids, culture media, and materials; therefore, their economic and environmental costs should not be neglected.

Final remarks

In conclusion, the report provides a solid evidence base and an ambitious policy roadmap. It could be improved even further by incorporating the following three aspects: i) defining clear short-term, mid-term, and long-term priorities for materials and relevant actions, ii) refining how to improve alignment mechanisms between research, regulation, and industrial scale-up, and iii) embedding educational, social, and ethical considerations, in addition to technical and economic ones. These proposals could help refine feasibility in the report, and identify quick wins and longer-term investments, starting from the list of policy options in Chapter 7. This list is a good starting point, but the basic research directions of Chapter 6 were not included.

Discussion

A working group member acknowledged and agreed that advanced materials are needed for improvements in any technology, and this should be included in the definition. This is related to the education topic brought up by the keynote speaker. Material science should be part of any engineering degree since any technology improvement requires materials.

An invited discussant questioned whether the report gives the impression that there are good and bad materials. The keynote speaker did not get that impression from the report. He further added that, rather than distinguishing between good and bad materials, a real challenge is identifying which materials are advanced materials. For example, many trivial materials can become advanced in the future if we invest resources to make them more sustainable. Therefore, adding a perspective on what to expect from materials in the short-, mid-, and long-term is relevant, since materials can evolve.

The co-chair appreciated the “trustworthy data” label proposed by the keynote. The keynote added that since there are no pathways to create trusted databases, it remains challenging for the working group to pinpoint them. Developing such a roadmap is critical for advanced materials development in future, and the experts and the working group can collectively brainstorm it.

Summary of recommendations

- Add a table of materials and systems discussed in the report, including any missing examples (materials and technologies), and rank them by EU position in relation to the international competition, potential societal and economic impact, and degree of maturity; provide a clear rationale for why they are considered advanced, and outline associated risks and benefits.
- The material-agnostic approach requested in the scoping paper is not appropriate; the report should adopt a global view to distinguish organic from inorganic materials and technologies, highlighting their fundamentally different properties, sustainability profiles, and implications for simulation and AI-driven innovation.
- Explain how curated, trusted databases will be developed, addressing the complexity of materials data, FAIR and trust aspects, EU-wide norms and standards, and short-, mid-, and long-term strategies such as EU-based trusted data foundries.
- Address societal and training aspects by embedding sustainability, AI/ML, innovation, and advanced materials science in curricula; promote EU-supported master's programmes and alliances, and leverage MOOCs, blended mobility, and competitions to build a workforce equipped for future challenges.
- Discuss possible conflicting goals, especially regarding societal acceptance of new technologies and address how to set priorities between them—examples: robust vs. efficient materials, geo-strategy vs. environmental protection, and social sustainability vs. industrial redevelopment.
- Consider economic feasibility and viability and economic impact for circularity and synthetic biology, noting challenges such as the higher cost and lower quality of recycled resins compared to virgin materials, and the resource-intensive nature of synthetic biology.
- Final remarks:
 - ▶ Define clear short-, medium-, and long-term priorities for materials and relevant actions.
 - ▶ Refine alignment mechanisms between research, regulations, and industrial scale-up.
 - ▶ Embed educational, social, and ethical considerations in addition to technical and economic ones.

Review of Chapter 2: A primer on sustainability: Concepts, processes, and best practices

Chapter overview

The chapter discusses advanced materials as sustainable materials, highlighting the importance of sustainability throughout the whole life cycle, from raw material sourcing to end-of-life. The increasing volume of raw materials extraction increases the need to consider supply chain security and minimising imports from outside Europe. Data are included to strengthen this point. The report then proposes and promotes policies that foster urban mining and all circular strategies.

When discussing sustainability, it is important to avoid green washing and carbon tunnel vision. Life-cycle assessment relies on holistic approaches, which include more categories than global warming potential. To estimate the sustainability of production processes for advanced materials, measuring environmental but also social and economic impacts is needed. Maintaining third-party access is important to make sure of the claims made about the production processes.

Some examples of strategies for sustainability of advanced materials are given, such as bio-based systems as an alternative to fossil raw materials. Examples include bio-based materials like bioplastic, which can be fully recycled. Other than stimulating circular production, making the use of primary resources more sustainable is also important.

Another sustainability strategy focused on the report is industrial symbiosis. A pioneering example are multi-storey buildings in Mariupol, Ukraine, which were built in the sixties and the seventies without using any conventional cement. They were, in fact, made from blast furnace slag, by-products of the steel industry in the region. Implementing by-product sharing between industries is encouraged, and AI approaches can be used to suggest the best matching over different industries.

Finally, the main key messages of the report were presented.

Summary of comments by the first discussant

The report is well-written, the whole picture of sustainability in relation to materials production was considered a tremendous effort.

The discussant considers that there is too much focus on green hydrogen and hydrogen economy in the report. Hydrogen it is not as green as desirable, and its potential to make a significant contribution at a commercial level remains unclear. Instead, research should focus on inexpensive, fully sustainable life-cycle hydrogen production. Conventional electrolysis is inefficient, and Europe's use of renewable electricity when compared to others is not a strong selling point due to current smart-charging practices for electric vehicles.

The speaker discussed two alarming trends. First, Greenland has been losing ice at a high rate over the past 10 years. As a consequence, sea levels will rise by 7.5 meters above current levels, threatening the

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whole planet. Without human intervention, the ice loss is highly likely to be irreversible. Therefore, the focus should be on interventions to prevent ice loss over the Arctic Circle region in the North Pole. The second concerning trend relates to the Earth's living systems, where about 200 species are disappearing every day. This is the human footprint on the planet, and the focus must be on mitigating these two challenges: climate change and biodiversity loss.

The CCAG proposed the 4R Planet strategy to: reduce emissions; remove excess greenhouse gases from the atmosphere at scale; repair climate systems, such as the North Pole; and build resilience. Materials can help achieve these objectives, and the report should identify pathways to achieve each of these strategies.

Our societies and economies are still dependent on fossil fuels, but the prices of renewable technologies are reducing. Solar panels have become cheap, drastically reducing the cost to produce a watt of electricity from them. Both electricity investment and the market for solar energy grew substantially over the last decade. Other areas of renewable electricity production, including nuclear energy, are growing. Collectively, these efforts have changed carbon emission trajectories, where most countries have decoupled emissions from GDP and population growth. Such efforts need to be accelerated, and the report should emphasise how technology and materials are crucial for those efforts.

Most people quote only carbon dioxide figures when assessing the level of greenhouse gas emissions in the atmosphere. However, over the last 20 years, methane has been more than one-third of the climate change problem, but this is not discussed in the report. It is important to focus on determining methane sources. For example, Europe now has a satellite that can capture methane sources, and most comes from oil, gas, and coal mining. Even the inactive old coal mines still emit methane. Since methane is relatively easy to convert into carbon dioxide, burning it into carbon dioxide is a smart strategy. However, the focus should be on removing methane. The half-life of methane in the atmosphere is 10 to 12 years and removing it from the atmosphere within the next two decades can lower average global temperatures.

Nature provides examples that can be imitated to remove greenhouse gas emissions at a largescale. When blue whales come to the ocean surface to breathe, they excrete a vast trail of faeces, which produces a green forest of phytoplankton. These phytoplankton absorb carbon dioxide and become food to fish, increasing biomass massively. With this life cycle, the blue whale population is restored to the levels of four hundred years ago. This research is being developed by the Marine Biomass Regeneration (MBR) project at the Centre for Climate and Repair (CCR). Another example by CCR is the Marine Cloud Brightening project, a collaborative effort to create white cloud cover over the North Sea and the Greenland area, to try to slow down the sun melting of ice in this region.

In conclusion, the report could have engaged the urgent need to solve the climate change crisis, which would have helped prioritise research focus on specific material functionalities.

Summary of comments by the second discussant

Chapter 2 is divided into five topical subchapters, which the discussant finds well selected. These are followed by a subchapter with specific examples and closes with a summary of the key messages. However, some asymmetries in the level of detail between different related sections are noted. For example, in Chapter 2.6., the section on electronics is one page long, whereas the section on construction spans four pages. The imbalance in the level of detail makes certain topics seem more important compared to others. The report should give justice to all the sections by presenting a similar level of detail.

In addition, it was noted that some figures are not readable.

Materials for sustainable energy are not organised and described properly. Some of them, such as high entropy alloys, are presented in Chapter 6 instead of Chapter 2. Moreover, presenting high entropy alloys as a case study gives a false impression that they are the only solution. Instead, there should be an overview of all the different advanced materials relevant to energy before presenting specific case studies. It should be clear that this is one case study among many others that cannot be treated in detail.

In Section 2.2., the LCA section was considered comprehensive and well-written, especially its valorisation of the multi-criteria lifecycle approach. Table 2 (Table 3 in the final draft) is presented to give an overview of this, but it is actually very valuable because it summarises the chapter. However, the caption does not accurately reflect its message and importance.

Repairability should be discussed in Section 2.3., focused on recycling.

Section 2.4. is confusing and needs revision. In addition, concepts such as “minimising fossil energy” and “freeing more carbon for materials production” are not ambitious enough. These solutions do not necessarily align fully with a carbon-zero economy.

In Section 2.5., it is unclear why the section on the transition to eco-electronics is part of the chapter. It needs more context, quantitative information, and references to identify the proportion of electronics that are eco-electronics.

Some examples are given where circularity is extremely important, such as the lunar settlement and the off-grid AtLAST telescope. However, they are very particular choices and might not be a good example to catch people's attention. Instead, examples that are more relatable to people should be used.

In Sections 2.6.4. and 2.6.5., the reference to the European projects as case studies is considered excellent and very convincing. However, there is an asymmetry in the level of detail. All projects should have the same level of detail, or they can be combined into a single section on European projects.

The connection with Chapter 6 is also mentioned. Energy materials are inherently part of a sustainability approach. However, it seems like the only suggested research direction would be hydrogen storage materials, while many energy-related aspects could be mentioned.

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The link between Chapter 2 and policy options in Chapter 7 is not well established. The basis for each policy option should be set in the chapter, and this was not completely done. In some cases, they are also framed more as recommendations than options, which is not adequate.

Discussion

An invited discussant questioned how to navigate which aspects are important in defining sustainability. Several important frameworks account for environmental, social, and economic aspects in addition to holistic multi-criteria decision analysis systems. It remains unclear who will decide which assessments are important and which are not. The first discussant answered with a suggestion to refer to the Brundtland Commission report, which originally defined sustainability after many deliberations. He emphasised that the final definition of sustainability should focus on practices to protect our ecosystems. He reiterated the example of whales, mentioning how the sun's energy and thermodynamics play a role in sustainability. He does not consider that the notion of sustainability poses a real challenge, as long as it is carefully thought through.

The co-chair gave a rationale for choosing the EU projects as examples in the report. The EU invests considerable amounts of money into flagship projects, and comparing their outcomes using quantitative measures will be useful. This could include sustainability aspects for the European projects.

The experts' comment on focusing on the other R strategies in addition to recyclability was well received by one working group member. The participant suggested discussing them and their consequences on manufacturing for different types of advanced materials in the report. Identifying Horizon Europe-funded recent projects and including them as examples in the report was also proposed.

Summary of recommendations

First discussant

- Reduce emphasis on hydrogen economy; focus on inexpensive, fully sustainable life-cycle hydrogen production.
- Emphasise urgent global challenges (climate change and biodiversity loss), to help prioritise research focus on specific material functionalities.
- Integrate the 4R Planet strategy (reduce, remove, repair, resilience) and outline material pathways for each.
- Emphasise how technology and materials are crucial for those efforts reduce dependency on fossil fuels and the prices of renewable technologies.
- Address methane as a major climate issue; include discussion on its sources and removal.
- Engage with nature-based solutions for large-scale greenhouse gas removal.

Second discussant

- Ensure balanced detail across sections (e.g., construction vs electronics, Section 2.6.).
- Improve readability of some figures throughout the chapter.
- Organise and properly describe materials for sustainable energy and avoid implying single-solution approaches, e.g., high entropy alloys are presented in Chapter 6 instead of Chapter 2 – provide an overview of advanced energy materials before presenting case studies; clarify that this is one case study among many others.
- Revise the caption of Table 2 (Section 2.2.) to reflect its importance and message accurately.
- Add reparability discussion in the recycling section (Section 2.3.).
- Revise Section 2.4. to make solutions more ambitious; avoid limited concepts like “minimising fossil energy”.
- Improve clarity and evidence in the eco-electronics section (Section 2.5.); add quantitative data and references.
- Replace particular examples related to circularity with others that are more relatable to people.
- Consolidate or expand references to EU projects into a dedicated section with consistent detail (Sections 2.6.4. and 2.6.5.).
- Clarify the connection to Chapter 6 and include other energy-related research topics.
- Strengthen the link between Chapter 2 and policy options in Chapter 7.

Review of Chapter 3: Digitalisation: Data, simulations, and AI

Chapter overview

The chapter focuses on digitalisation in advanced materials, particularly on data, simulation, and AI aspects. The importance of data is often overstated at present due to the lack of high-quality, useful data in public databases. People in the audience were encouraged to share whether they rely on publicly available data for in their research. Structural data of inorganic materials are considered to have been somewhat useful, and protein data banks enormously useful, but proteins are still very different from the topic of advanced materials. For example, public databases report a range of temperatures for the melting temperature of tungsten, so any technological or academic research that is based on the data that are available is not reliable at this stage. In the speakers' view, this overstated importance is due to the appeal of the FAIR acronym, encouraging the audience to share examples where it proved useful.

Simulation is one of the few areas where Europe is a world leader. Both the US and China run simulation codes for materials that were developed in Europe.

AI will quickly change everything, probably faster than expected. For example, in certain fields, ChatGPT-5 Thinking can provide objective high-quality analysis and reasoning, without the risk of bias from individual researchers, albeit quality assurance against hallucinations is still needed. .

Summary of comments by the first discussant

A first point in his review relates to the general mindset and importance of having a clear vision on the relevance of advanced materials for competitiveness in Europe. The purpose of making advanced materials is to enable new functionalities or improve their performance. In addition, the advanced materials need to be manufacturable at competitive cost and in a sustainable and energy efficient manner, and companies should be able to adopt and monetise them fast.

The working group constructed a very good chapter, separating it into data, simulations, and AI sections. These three pillars are Europe's core strengths. While most of the critical aspects are covered, a few areas could be strengthened, and some ideas need to be emphasised further. For instance, the concept of digital twins in relation to machine learning models are not sharply defined. The use of data in the context of simulations could be further emphasised as a strength in research and the economy in Europe. The chapter should elaborate on the existing ability in Europe to link European data spaces, data creators, and infrastructure through APIs and handshaking. On the AI and data dimension, leveraging rapidly evolving AI models is important; we can design and discover materials that are not only advanced for a specific functionality but also based on accessible materials that can be sourced locally and reliably, to ensure the resilience and security of supply. This point relates to sovereignty, an important aspect that could be presented more strongly in the report. The report needs to make clear that FAIR data also has to be useful. Currently, most data are not FAIR, but FAIR data has to advance and

accelerate materials discovery. Without this, there is a risk that most of the advanced materials that will be put into production over the next 10-20 years have already been discovered, because that is the turnaround for inorganic deep tech materials. Without the use of simulations and AI, a 20-year materials discovery-to-commercialisation cycle will take place. These tools must be used, and a new European strength needs to be built. Finally, existing data has too much focus in the chapter as compared to fast generation of high quality curated and FAIR data. Existing data puts a strong emphasis on LLM-utilisation of existing (non-curated) data, and the chapter would benefit from discussing the speed and form of data generation more and the instant ontologising of data upon creation.

Some more strategic recommendations for the chapter include the need to further highlight the existence of several data generators/providers in Europe, whether it is large-scale facilities or initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and Materials Commons aimed at building a pan-European infrastructure of infrastructures. In regard to sovereignty, there should be a stronger link to what is being done both on the hardware and software side. For example, the RAISE (Resource for Artificial Intelligence Science in Europe) programme and AI gigafactories ensure that European researchers and startups have access to competitive and state-of-the-art hardware and software. Another key aspect that needs mentioning is the shortening of the time between discovery and commercially viable products through in-lab and cross-lab validation of AI predictions, e.g. using federated self-driving laboratories. Europe already has many ongoing initiatives to create pan-European networks for this purpose, e.g. Materials Commons. Having only a world-class material is not enough; the optimisation at the device-level is also important for Europe's competitiveness. The chapter should also emphasise talent and skills development to upgrade the existing and future workforce in AI for advanced materials. Others have already made this suggestion. Europe needs to leverage its fundamental research and innovation excellence, at the MCSA and ERC levels, but also in European research groups doing great innovation. On sustainability, recyclability-by-design concepts are already making their way into simulation and AI for science and materials. Finally, internationalisation should be highlighted. The EU should strengthen advanced materials partnerships, especially with associate member states, and create a pan-European infrastructure.

As a conclusion, the speaker notes that a key challenge to competitiveness in AI for materials discovery is that talented people and startups move to the US. American startups in this space raise hundreds of millions of dollars. Europe should leverage AI and its talent to predict unknown materials and unknown processing in material development.

Summary of comments by the second discussant

The chapter constitutes an excellent summary of the state of play. Digitisation in material science is transforming the field, benefiting many actors, including large corporates, startups, and research institutes.

There are a few challenges in the field and highlighting them can strengthen the chapter. There is a host of data from industries that is currently not accessible. How to leverage all that data to develop a fully-

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fledged generative AI model for advanced materials is a key question. Leveraging startups, which tend to be good intermediaries between large corporations and other players, can be a solution.

Another important aspect relates to data being typically present in heterogeneous formats, such as datasets, metadata, and graphs, across different disciplines. Ideally, data types should be machine-readable and contextualised by AI algorithms.

Metadata needs to be strengthened, and standardisation might be useful here to ensure reproducibility and a general standard.

What organisational challenges and changes should be adopted to have a fully-fledged AI system in laboratories is another key question. People with skills in advanced materials and AI are required in the short run. In the long run, we need to think about who will run laboratories in the future. Training needs can be evaluated based on whether laboratory assistants and technicians will still be part of laboratories.

Another relevant point relates to how the startup world mimics the evolution of digitalisation in other fields. It progressed from simple machine learning to unstructured data, to relational databases and ontologies, to finally slowly using deep learning and neural networks for materials discovery. The next step would be having fully self-driven autonomous labs, where experiments that cannot be simulated are actually conducted by robots under the guidance of AI. The further evolution impinges on quantum technologies. Companies and startups are already working with quantum algorithms to support materials discovery. For example, Kipu Quantum, present throughout Europe, develops specialised algorithms for research leveraging quantum technologies.

Finally, having standardised data from across the world is hugely beneficial to train algorithms. However, over-standardisation can hamper flexibility and innovation. Therefore, minimum viable standards are required for metadata, based on the provenance and trustworthiness of data, along with sustainability and circular economy criteria.

To conclude, some additional recommendations were proposed to support the digitalisation efforts: investment in federated infrastructures; incentives to work on AI harmonisation tools, such as AI that helps translate data into a minimum viable standard, need to be created; collaboration with industry for data usage should be strengthened; a strategy should be in place for the time when quantum technologies become widely available; and a mid- and long-term digitalisation strategy in the advanced materials sector should be built, including the organisational/skills aspect.

Discussion

A discussant disagreed with the chapter lead and specified that FAIR data are already widely used in chemistry, physics, and biology research to perform simulation and modelling work. For example, data in life sciences are becoming increasingly FAIR, and bioinformatics is successful largely because of the availability of verified data, even long before the term was coined. Nano-safety data are also becoming FAIR, and Europe is the leader in its verification, which can be instrumental in AI and data-driven modelling and simulations. Another possible description of FAIR is findable and AI-ready; however, this

definition does not have trust aspects integrated into it. Whether these AI-based safe and sustainable assessments, modelling, and simulations of innovation are trustable will always be a question, and this is where metadata (in the classical term, the FAIR term) comes in. Provenance is essential for trusting data, and it must be preserved regardless of the technologies used. Overall, safety needs to be built into the AI-driven modelling and not be a standalone aspect in advanced materials innovation. A working group member corroborated these points. In his view, a key consideration is not only embedding safety from the start in data pipelines, but also distinguishing between good results and trustworthy results, suggesting a degree of caution. He also suggested making a distinction between evidence that will be convincing to scientists and evidence that will be convincing for lawyers, and questions whether AI-generated data and materials will withstand legal scrutiny.

The first discussant agreed with the second one in what regards the importance of federated self-driving labs. A large inorganic materials centre requires millions of euros in funding, which is not sufficient to interlink many European centres of excellence. He recommended utilising simulations to deploy experiments across different platforms and use AI to analyse the data and bring it back to the ecosystem. Europe has a data edge in that regard and should use it. Data-sharing is not equally developed in other parts of the world. A discussant noted that, although an algorithm can produce false results, it can also greatly improve reproducibility—an issue in many areas of science where data have not been validated across different labs or sufficiently tested. Without this validation, it is difficult to de-risk industry uptakes.

A question was posed about the massive energy requirement for data centres and who would pay for it. Nowadays, the equivalent to Japan's entire current power demand is needed just to run the EU data. There are also critical material requirements for building data centre infrastructure and power stations, but none of these aspects are mentioned in the report. Resilience is often noted, but where the material and power to run all of this is not clear. A working group member brought up ultra-low power-consuming devices to solve this challenge. For example, nanomorphous materials can store information using 1,000 times less energy than a conventional SIMO device. He suggested that challenges could be turned into opportunities in the future using such technologies. A discussant suggests looking at the top 500 in sustainable computing, where Europe has the top five places at the minimum. This is an area where Europe has an advantage. The chapter lead remarked that the chapter is about data for materials—which represents a small fraction of the use of supercomputer resources and energy—and not about materials for data, that is, materials that support the AI/information and communication technologies (ICT) and energy technologies.

Summary of recommendations

First discussant

- Highlight the strategic importance of advanced materials for Europe's competitiveness, including performance, adoption, manufacturability, sustainability, and monetisation.
- Strengthen the definition and role of digital twins in relation to machine learning models.

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- Emphasise the use of data in simulations as a European strength and elaborate on linking European data spaces, data creators, and infrastructure through APIs and handshaking.
- Make clear that FAIR data must be useful and accelerate materials discovery; address the risk of a 20-year discovery cycle without AI and simulations.
- Balance the focus between existing data and new data generation, including instant ontologising of data upon creation.
- Highlight European data generators/providers and link sovereignty efforts on hardware and software.
- Include strategies to shorten the time between discovery and commercially viable products through in-lab and cross-lab validation of AI predictions using self-driving laboratories.
- Emphasise optimisation at the device level, not only material level, to ensure competitiveness.
- Strengthen the link to RAISE and the focus on talent and skills development for AI in advanced materials to upgrade the workforce.
- Highlight sustainability aspects such as recyclability by design in AI and simulation approaches.
- Address internationalisation: strengthen partnerships with associate member states and create pan-European infrastructure through Materials Commons.

Second discussant

- Highlight the challenges in the field by including, for example, strategies to leverage industry data, which is currently inaccessible, and consider startups as intermediaries.
- Address heterogeneity of data formats (datasets, metadata, graphs) and ensure they are machine-readable and contextualised by AI algorithms.
- Strengthen metadata and consider standardisation for reproducibility, while avoiding over-standardisation.
- Discuss organisational challenges for implementing fully-fledged AI systems in labs, including short-term skills needs and long-term roles.
- Highlight the evolution of digitalisation in other fields, e.g. toward self-driven autonomous labs and the role of robotics for experiments that cannot be simulated; address the emerging role of quantum technologies and specialised algorithms for materials discovery; include examples such as Kipu Quantum.
- Define minimum viable standards based on provenance, trustworthiness, and sustainability criteria.

Additional recommendations:

- Recommend investment in federated infrastructures.
- Recommend incentives for AI harmonisation tools.
- Strengthen collaboration with industry for data usage.
- Develop a mid- and long-term digitalisation strategy for advanced materials, including organisational and skills aspects.

Review of Chapter 4: Emerging technologies in manufacturing, scaling, and infrastructure

Chapter overview

The chapter presents manufacturing, scaling, and infrastructure, along with emerging production technologies on advanced materials. Its focus derives from the scoping questions, covering topics such as sustainability, scaling, focusing energy, mobility, construction, and others.

The chapter contains six key messages:

1. Emerging materials are essential for driving the green and digital transition across the construction, energy, mobility, electronics, and healthcare sectors. These materials must be multi-functional, sustainable, and scalable.
2. Advanced manufacturing technologies are critical in producing next-generation materials with enhanced properties and circularity.
3. Scalability remains a significant challenge when moving materials from the laboratory to the market.
4. Innovation ecosystems and networks are vital to bridging the lab-to-market gap and promoting cross-sector collaborations. Innovation sandboxes and learning factories provide low-risk environments for testing and scaling of materials and processes. These platforms also foster collaboration between academia, industry, and regulators.
5. Digital tools, such as digital twins, simulations, and AI, predict scalability issues, optimise processes, and accelerate certification and market entry.
6. Material design must shift from composition-based to microstructure-driven approaches when developing sustainable alloys and electroceramics, integrating AI, robotic, and circularity principles.

On this topic, the following evidence-based policy options are proposed:

- Fund regional innovation sandboxes to support real-world testing of advanced materials and manufacturing processes, especially for small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and startups.
- Create modular, scalable infrastructure hubs for bioproduction and advanced manufacturing, offering shared access to pilot-scale equipment, digital twins, and AI tools.
- Support interdisciplinary R&D programs integrating materials science, biotechnology, AI, and engineering, especially those using the design-build-test-learn (DBTL) cycle.
- Incentivise circular material design through funding schemes prioritising microstructure-driven alloy development and utilising e-waste and scrap materials.
- Strengthen collaboration between academia and industry by increasing support for research transfer organisations (RTOs), knowledge transfer organisations, and competitiveness clusters, with performance-based funding tied to innovation transfer metrics.
- Incentivise circular materials design through funding schemes.

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- Strengthen collaboration between academia and industry.
- Accelerate certification and regulatory pathways for advanced materials by involving regulators early in sandbox environments and harmonising standards across EU member states.
- Fund the development of digital twins, simulation platforms, and AI-based process optimisation tools to promote digital integration in manufacturing.
- Invest in biofoundries and synthetic biology platforms and establish regulatory frameworks that enable safe and scalable biological materials production.
- Develop standardised LCA methodologies for bio-based materials to streamline regulatory approval and industrial adoption.
- Launch public procurement programs (PCPs) to reduce the risk associated with emerging technologies and create early market opportunities for sustainable materials.

As a final remark, the speaker noted the need to improve the pictures and address cross-referencing.

Summary of comments by the first discussant

The chapter discusses emerging technologies in manufacturing, scaling, and infrastructure. It attempts to answer the following questions: how can materials be manufactured, what production technologies should be used in their manufacturing, and how these technologies can be scaled up.

The chapter starts with a table in Section 4.2.1. outlining various sectors and functions required for advanced materials in those sectors. It is through the lens of this table and the defined materials that manufacturing is then discussed. Several comments are made in this regard. Rather than defining specific materials, the table should focus on functions and delivery methods for those functions, which may or may not be the currently known materials. It was also considered useful to set classes of materials rather than specific materials in this section, and to discuss cross-sectoral resources management for them, as an understanding is needed on whether resources are available to scale up production of specific materials.

Several sector-specific concerns can also be resolved to strengthen this table. In the construction sector, while the desired functions for the advanced materials are well known, the solutions are not well adopted due to the lack of data on long-term performance of materials. For example, developing faster testing methods for construction materials is necessary. The mobility sector requires an increased production of materials. This notion could be linked with circularity and other business models on how to develop the mobility sector in general to avoid having to scale up expensive materials so much.

Sections 4.2.2. and 4.2.3. focus on biotechnology and synthetic biology. In biotechnology, the two key aspects of sustainability and scalability are not addressed. The chapter states, quite optimistically, that biotechnology produces sustainable materials, which is justified by the fact that it largely reduces carbon emissions. However, these statements represent a tunnel vision, as other impacts might be compromised. In the discussion around synthetic biology, the DBTL cycle is not unique to this field. This approach should be expanded to other materials as well, such as digital development/discovery

laboratories in small molecules, materials, formulations, medicines, and bioprocessing methods. Finally, the lack of supply at scale is the main problem in adopting bio-based materials and small molecules at present. There are only a handful of suppliers who can produce multiple bio-derived molecules/materials at a sufficient scale to have any impact on the overall Scope 3 emissions of the materials supply chain. Biofoundries are discussed in Section 4.2.3., but they should be split out into a separate section and linked to resource analysis, bio-waste, and bio-refineries.

In Section 4.2.4., sustainability is only discussed for alloys, but it should cover all materials, instead of being a subsection of specific materials. Modelling methods are also under alloys but should be set as a general section.

Section 4.3. focuses on scalability challenges. It starts by stating that scaling up some of the novel solutions is not always feasible because of expensive precursors. However, it should be noted that these pathways will never be scalable, so alternative materials with similar functions, improved efficiency or alternative methods of manufacturing should be sought. Second, a differentiation should be made between the scalability of, for example, biopolymers and materials for batteries. While production of bulk polymers may be scaled up by adjusting production capacity, the use of complex advanced materials most likely would be justified only if functional efficiencies are significantly improved, as due to thermodynamics their production is unavoidably more energy intensive and has lower production rates. For example, Figure 3 (Figure 8 in the final ERR) demonstrates how advanced materials and processing methods increase energy consumption and reduce production rates. Third, the sections mention two methods of scaling—the numbering up of small units or increasing the size of a single unit—but advanced manufacturing technologies, such as process intensification (PI), should be added. PI allows for a dramatic increase in the throughput of small units, such that a single small unit can sometimes be much more efficient than a large one, as has been demonstrated in chemicals and materials manufacturing. Finally, resilience in supply chains is not addressed in the section, although it is addressed in the sustainability section.

In Section 4.3.2., an example on lean manufacturing suggests that made-to-order is not a scalable and efficient model. However, this model is gaining success due to AI technologies and new business models are being developed.

Summary of comments by the second discussant

Before delving into the chapter, a comment is made regarding the definition of advanced materials in the introduction of the report. The main criticism is related to the timeline. When talking about developing new advanced materials or investments for upscaling in industry, time is crucial, and this was not found in the report. On the critical materials topic, the EU has invested large amounts of money, time, and effort to define and understand criticality, but this aspect is not well reflected in the document. The report also uses several different terms—such as scarce, rare, and critical—interchangeably.

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In Chapter 4, the main questions are: i) how things can be produced, and ii) how much they are going to cost—considering that costs cover different layers, such as investments, financial and environmental costs. Again, the timing of when new advanced materials will be developed and when investments for upscaling will become available is not addressed. In the Critical Raw Materials Act and the Net-Zero Industry Act, 2030 was set as a timeline, a bit ambitiously. How alignment with that timeline is possible is not clear. It remains unclear whether financial investment will be available in such a short timeframe. It is also not specified in the report who will bear the cost of producing advanced materials. The report also fails to mention the difficulty of securing large investments for ambitious ventures.

The construction section only discusses building structure and some interior components. However, buildings also have heating and cooling, power systems, digital units, water, and other materials, which are all energy-consuming. These components are not discussed in the report. The chapter identifies circular strategies; however, it largely focuses on recycling. This is the lowest and most energy-consuming circular strategy, which also degrades materials. The report should discuss product life extension and remanufacturing, along with the technologies required to achieve them. Again, a very narrow view of what is called construction is presented. The report presents many examples of advanced materials, but it fails to illustrate whether these materials will solve existing problems. For example, neodymium and dysprosium are essential for magnets, yet the report focuses on wind turbines and plates, which are important but not critical to keeping Europe's power systems running. Without magnets, there is no power. A critique is also made on the inclusion of robotics, AI, and automation in the report, as they are all critical-raw-materials-hungry, needing much power (renewable) and digital technology.

Section 4.3. addresses scalability challenges. While the text focuses on business, there is no mention of investors, or member states who will do the main investment, rather than the EU. The proposals made in the report are all high risk for investors. No numbers are provided regarding, for example, the investment size, sources, or timescales. The Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) were set up to deal with the 'valley of death' and bridging RTOs, universities, companies, and startups, but they failed. It is unclear if this report proposes to replace KIC with other mechanisms.

Finally, in Chapter 7 on policy options, the challenging 2030 deadline should be addressed.

Discussion

The co-chair agrees with using the term "crucial" instead of "scarce", but remarked that many definitions change and evolve over time, such as the use of "upcycling" instead of "manufacturing". This can be easily addressed in the report, for example by adding a glossary to define important concepts. The co-chair also remarked that while it is difficult to identify a timeline for future projects, industries evolve very fast these days and materials are immediately manufactured and scaled for applications. Belief in disruptive innovation is needed. Another working group member agreed as well that the absence of a timeline is quite fair, because it depends on many complex factors. While dates are relevant for policymakers, putting different temporalities into play is considered more relevant in this context.

A working group member pointed out that scaling up a technology or a company depends on different factors. Technological readiness level is relevant, but also customer readiness level, and investment readiness level are also important pillars in the market acceptance of any product. The motivation of engineers, customers, and investors also varies. Ultimately, the market requires a product and not a material. Therefore, product development in parallel with material development is required. China is doing this in scientific and technological parks, and the EU needs this ecosystem, along with startups and SMEs. Another working group member agreed with this idea and suggested identifying policies to implement the novel technologies for manufacturing the devices of the future.

The co-chair of the working group highlighted the main difference between the EU, China, and the US to explain why product development is slow. In China and the US, the military is the first customer for many materials and products. The EU does not have such a mechanism.

The chapter lead responds to the second discussant, noting, on the “critical” definition question, that this is changing continuously: in two years from now the position may be different to today. Regarding the policies question and whether the working group proposes to change the KIT, he considers that these relate to the general policy of the European Union, as it is such a huge discussion. The working group is tasked to point the path, not to suggest structural policy changes. The second discussant concludes by remarking that, since this report is in preparation for the Advanced Materials Act, the timeline aspect is critical to make this document a useful policy instrument.

Summary of recommendations

First discussant

- In the sector-function table (Section 4.2.1):
 - ▶ Focus on functions and delivery methods rather than specific materials; consider grouping by classes of materials and include cross-sectoral resource management to assess scalability.
 - ▶ Address sector-specific gaps: For construction, develop faster testing methods to provide long-term performance data; for mobility, link increased material production to circularity and alternative business models to reduce reliance on scaling expensive materials.
- In Sections 4.2.2. and 4.2.3., address sustainability and scalability in biotechnology; broaden synthetic biology discussion beyond carbon reduction; apply DBTL cycle to other fields; tackle supply chain limitations; and create a separate section for biofoundries linked to resource analysis and bio-refineries.
- In Section 4.2.4., move sustainability and modelling methods out of alloy-specific subsections and make them general sections covering all materials.
- In Section 4.3., clarify that some pathways will never be scalable; propose alternatives; differentiate scalability for bulk polymers vs complex advanced materials; include process intensification as a method; and address supply chain resilience.
- In Section 4.3.2., revisit the example on lean manufacturing: clarify that made-to-order models may become scalable with AI and new business models.

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Second discussant

- Define timelines for developing advanced materials and scaling investments; align with EU targets (e.g., 2030 in Critical Raw Materials Act and Net-Zero Industry Act).
- Clarify terminology: avoid using scarce, rare, and critical interchangeably; reflect EU work on criticality.
- Discuss cost layers (investment, financial, environmental) and specify who bears the cost of producing advanced material; address the difficulty of securing large investments for ambitious ventures; include numbers on investment size, sources, and timescales.
- Expand construction section to include heating/cooling, power systems, digital units, water, and other energy-consuming components.
- Broaden circular strategies beyond recycling; include product life extension and remanufacturing and the technologies needed.
- Ensure examples of advanced materials illustrate how they solve critical problems (e.g., magnets for power systems, not just wind turbines).
- Discuss the resource intensity of robotics, AI, and automation (critical raw materials and renewable energy demand).
- In scalability (Section 4.3.), mention investors and member states as key actors; clarify high-risk nature of proposals and address the lack of numbers.
- Explain whether the report proposes alternatives to KICs for bridging the valley of death.
- In policy options (Chapter 7), address the challenging 2030 deadline explicitly.

Review of Chapter 5: Policy, legislation, and governance of innovation ecosystems

Chapter overview

The chapter provides an overview of the regulatory and policy landscape related to the governance of advanced materials and presents a foundation for policy options that could be considered by decision-makers in the future. The chapter first gives a historical background on different kinds of enterprises that led to scientific innovation in the past. For example, large private governmental laboratories were responsible for research and innovation in advanced materials in the 1950s, 60s, and 70s. During this time, no government-funded programmes influenced research in advanced materials on a large scale. On the other hand, large, national research programmes that heavily focused on precursors to advanced materials emerged in the 80s and 90s. This led to research advancements in biotechnology, information and communication technologies, nanotechnology, and others. Controversies related to scientific and technical aspects followed as research in these disciplines advanced. For example, genetically modified organisms were considered disasters in the public eye, and diverse views on public narratives were communicated in this chapter.

A substantial part of the chapter lays out the current regulatory landscape for advanced materials. The chapter also explains how multifaceted and multidimensional a term “advanced materials” is. Some categories, such as nanotechnology or nanomaterials, have been well-regulated in the past 25 years. On the contrary, for other materials there is also a lack of regulation, which is concerning to some extent. There is less information available on the risks associated with advanced materials other than nanomaterials.

The chapter features a review completed by consultancies for the European Commission in 2018 that investigated the pros and cons of advanced material regulation, especially focusing on environmental regulation. This review identified concerns related to two specific categories of advanced materials: nanomaterials and advanced polymers. Advanced polymers are different from regular plastics or polymers: they can walk across the floor, into and out of a bottle, and continue walking across the floor, based on external stimulation. Many people underestimate what it actually means to be advanced in such cases.

The chapter also discusses various certification and standardisation efforts that the European Commission has adopted in recent years, including strategies mentioned by the keynote speaker.

The final part of the chapter is dedicated to known or foreseen challenges in advanced materials. This includes the following important points: i) how to define advanced materials; ii) what are the different classes of advanced materials; iii) what data and information requirements are needed to perform hazard exposure and risk assessment; iv) what monitoring requirements should be mandated by the regulators as advanced materials come to the market and as society begins to use them; and v) what enforcement mechanisms would be appropriate. Since there are many different categories of advanced

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materials and diverse policy options, tools that work for one advanced material might not work for others. This makes the regulation of advanced materials a complex problem to solve.

The chapter also outlines parallels with nanomaterial regulation that started 25-30 years ago. For example, the definition of advanced materials is discussed. It took 10-15 years for the European Commission and others to define nanomaterials appropriately. Not having a definition was a bottleneck for all the subsequent regulatory actions.

The key message of the chapter is that the lessons learned from nanotechnology should be adopted for advanced materials to accelerate progress. Therefore, the speaker strongly warns against proposing a definition of advanced materials in the report. The OECD and other well-established institutions have already proposed definitions of advanced materials.

Summary of comments by the first discussant

The discussant agreed that lessons learned from decades of nano-safety expertise must be brought on board more clearly in the report. They referred to a paper by the joint expertise of the Network for Safe and Sustainable Development of Chemicals and Materials (NSC), formerly known as the NanoSafety Cluster, presenting a roadmap for advanced materials, and SSbD approaches based on lessons learned over the past two decades of nanomaterials research and regulation.

Several important recommendations to improve the report were then offered, in particular regarding Chapter 5, but many comments apply to other parts of the report as well. First, safety is a prerequisite for sustainability and circularity. It is not possible to have recyclable and reusable materials that are not safe or applied in safe ways. Therefore, safety needs to be a default aspect of sustainability and innovation, and it should be highlighted in all the chapters.

Second, FAIR data needs to be considered, especially with innovation in AI becoming more pronounced. Besides being machine-readable, FAIR data should be trusted, verifiable, and transparent, as mentioned by the keynote speaker. Trust and transparency can be automated with FAIR data and can become a part of the traceability aimed for these materials, and this chapter, along with Chapter 3 on digital AI, need to incorporate this aspect better. The AI-driven aspects of innovation and designing materials can quite easily represent low-hanging fruits for integrating lessons learned from toxicology into the innovation process. Making the SSbD approach a default early in the design process, before legislation, is a path forward.

Third, the SSbD framework needs to build on FAIR data, which should be iteratively reusable. Even with AI, which is solving many of the questions on how to manage the complexity, we still need to ensure that the provenance is included in the process, with proper trustworthy implementation.

Fourth, all stakeholders have a shared responsibility when it comes to resources. There is a need to include different approaches to support shared responsibility, including e.g. co-funding for the development and regulatory acceptance of novel approaches, including new approach methodologies (NAMs). In addition, the implementation of SSbD approaches that prepare innovations for current

regulatory criteria is central, and supports the advancement towards better and more straightforward regulation. The report could also reference ongoing efforts that the Commission is driving or supporting, such as the EU Roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments and the EU test method and validation strategy. The chapter describes the Malta Initiative, aiming to prioritise development and validation of test methods for nanomaterials and advanced materials, which is considered very good.

Regulatory preparedness is key when it comes to ensuring safe and sustainable advanced materials and relates to the need for revisable definitions and lessons learned from nano-safety. Definitions are often evolving, which makes it difficult to meet regulatory objectives and requirements. Therefore, the preparedness needs to come with an acknowledgement that there will always be gaps. Communication on these aspects can be strengthened through diverse approaches, including the concept of regulatory sandboxing. Whether this approach works for advanced materials remains unknown. Nevertheless, it is important to note that sandboxes need to be a safe space for all stakeholders, including for industry, regulators, and other communities. Liabilities and resource requirements need to be robustly clarified before sandboxes are established.

Mindset change in innovation processes needs to be emphasised. For example, material characterisation data are often equally useful for both functionality and safety assessments, i.e. characterisation data can be used in the prediction of functionalities as well as toxicities. These aspects should increasingly be researched and emphasised not only when training innovators, but also basic scientists in material science. Safety should be considered a strong driver of competitiveness alongside sustainability.

Finally, regulatory and market incentives for including safety and sustainability data and fostering SSbD-based business models are important for all the aspects indicated above. Communication and transdisciplinarity is key and should not be underestimated.

Summary of comments by the second discussant

Before starting, the speaker offered three caveats: i) the views expressed are their own; ii) advanced materials are not their area of expertise, despite their extensive work in risk and law; and iii) the comments are not limited to Chapter 5, but put in the context of the whole report.

Three points were pointed out: i) the remit of the report; ii) the dangers of wishful thinking; and iii) the importance of being thick, not thin, in one's analysis. First, the report addresses many challenging questions. It is important to explicitly engage with those questions and with what those questions are not asking, explicitly or implicitly. For example, the questions raised in the chapter do not necessarily raise the issue of regulation, but the report rightfully engages with regulation. In addition, the questions bring forth two particular dangers. First, there is a danger of trying to answer questions where evidence is not always available. Secondly, there is a focus on solutions, rather than truly understanding the question, which is discerning the practices around advanced materials.

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The report explores what advanced materials are, while recognising that it is difficult to do so. But it misses underlying what the practices are around advanced materials. This can be made explicit. The answer to one of the scoping questions (what contribution can advanced materials bring to EU strategic autonomy?) depends on the practices around which advanced materials are developed and brought to market. This is where law is really important because it creates the rules of the game, for competition and safety. Therefore, the definition of advanced materials is crucial since regulatory obligations rely on it.

Any regulatory area of risk can easily fall into the dangers of wishful thinking. In this report, but also in other documentation on advanced materials, there is often a shift from whether advanced materials *could* enhance the EU's strategic autonomy to whether they *can, will or should* achieve that. It is important to include solid evidence on that in the report to strengthen policy conclusions or recommendations. This evidence needs to be discussed with short-, medium-, and long-term views.

The final point relates to thinking in thick terms, not thin terms. The report states that advanced materials need evidence-based regulation and not over-regulation. This statement implies that evidence-based will always be less regulated rather than over-regulation. This creates a binary. In reality, a regulatory process grounded in understanding advanced materials and their risks and benefits is necessary to use any materials. This requires not only a set of rules, but also building institutions with diverse expertise in this discipline. While there is a temptation to talk in terms of assessment, such as life cycle and sustainability assessments, it is crucial to interrogate any kind of solution and think in an evidence-based manner. Nonetheless, whether advanced materials regulation needs new thinking or should be based on other examples remains an open question.

In conclusion, it is necessary to identify the remit of the report, avoid the dangers of wishful thinking and ensure ideas are grounded in a firm understanding of advanced materials, and finally, particularly when it comes to regulation, think in a thick way, not just about thin assessment processes.

Discussion

The keynote speaker asked for a description of thinking thick versus thin. Thick regulation can be very broad, and relies on shared responsibilities of the stakeholders, and he wonders if the definition of thick versus thin is aligned with this idea. The invited discussant explained that risk regulation in particular tends to be thought of in terms of a toolbox approach (e.g. the use of risk assessment, market-based mechanisms) rather than considering what institutions are needed to make it work and what expertise those institutions require. Usually, effective regulation requires a diverse range of expertise.

An invited discussant remarked several contradictions and overlaps in the report, when it comes to alignment with other acts, particularly the Critical Raw Material Act, Net-Zero Industry Act, and the Circular Economy Act (still in progress but ahead of the Advanced Materials Act). The second discussant agreed, noting that such overlap is common when new legislation is introduced. She further emphasised the importance of clearly defining the report's remit and specifying what further work remains.

The chapter lead agreed with the first discussant on the importance of reviewing the development of nanotechnology in terms of publications and lessons learned, but cautioned that the chapter should not focus solely on nanotechnology, as all the 22-23 categories of advanced materials deserve equal attention. He also questioned whether the second discussant supported using “less than ideal” definitions well accepted within the scientific and technological community, versus trying to develop a new perfect definition, noting that this was not fully achieved with nanomaterials. The second discussant emphasised that no definition will be perfect, as all are contested and have legal or regulatory implications. What matters is that any definition is grounded in reality and evidence-based, and aligned with the legal framework that is being created. The chapter lead further questioned the need for measurement, and the discussant noted that the point is to recognise that the definition is important, but is very much related to the framework that is being developed. While a quantitative definition is an option, there are a many good examples of non-quantitative definitions.

Summary of recommendations

First discussant

- Point to lessons learned from nanomaterials safety research and regulation.
- Make safety a prerequisite for sustainability and circularity; safety should be highlighted across all chapters.
- Strengthen the integration of FAIR data in AI-driven innovation: ensure data are machine-readable, trusted, verifiable, and transparent to support traceability; emphasise that FAIR data must be iteratively reusable and include provenance; incorporate lessons learned from toxicology and nano-safety into AI-driven materials design; make SSbD a default early in the design process, before legislation.
- Highlight shared responsibility for resources and regulatory implementation among stakeholders; regulators cannot allocate all resources alone; discuss ongoing EU efforts such as animal-free testing and new approach methodologies (e.g., Malta Initiative).
- Address regulatory preparedness for evolving definitions; acknowledge gaps and strengthen communication, for example through sandboxing, ensuring that these are a safe space for all stakeholders.
- Promote mindset change in innovation processes: link safety data with functionality data and emphasise this in training for innovators and scientists.
- Mention the need for regulatory and market incentives for safety and sustainability. The EU market should continue to be recognised for its high quality, safe and sustainable products, including advanced materials.

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Second discussant

- Clarify the remit of the report: state what questions it addresses and what it does not; avoid answering where evidence is lacking and avoid focusing on solutions rather than understanding practices around advanced materials.
- Avoid wishful thinking: base conclusions on solid evidence, include short-, medium-, and long-term perspectives, and strengthen discussion on practices and definitions (including the definition of advanced materials, as regulatory obligations depend on it).
- Adopt a thick approach to analysis: avoid binary framings (evidence-based vs over-regulation), go beyond thin assessments (e.g., LCA), and ground regulation in deep understanding of risks and benefits. Build institutions with diverse expertise and interrogate solutions in an evidence-based manner.

Review of Chapter 6: Basic research directions for future transition

Chapter overview

The chapter focuses on how fundamental science can help identify new materials for different applications. Fundamental research provides the tools to look for different functionalities and synthetic approaches to innovate new products and technologies. The broader point made in the chapter is that basic research offers completely new perspectives on specific applications that are previously unknown, in addition to being a tool of discovery. Understanding the mechanisms and fundamental processes provides the knowledge to transform society.

The chapter is broad in its scope, and maps how basic or fundamental research directions will move towards future transition. This point is expanded by showcasing numerous examples of advanced materials that will have applications in future. After presenting the scope of the chapter, successive sections describe bio-based materials, green energy, lighter materials, and others, explaining how these less explored materials and functionalities can become an advanced material product to solve challenges of our times.

Summary of comments by the first discussant

Overall, the chapter is considered to be very well written, but two aspects need to be included. First, advanced materials development should always include process development to ensure that innovative properties can be reliably and efficiently translated into scalable, real-world applications. Without a tailored process, even the most promising materials may fail to perform consistently or be economically viable. Integrating process development early also accelerates time-to-market and reduces risks during scale-up and manufacturing. Therefore, the report should note that process development is important for advanced materials and Europe's competitiveness. Second, sustainability and criticality are vital in the development of advanced materials to ensure responsible resource use and long-term availability. Moreover, technological openness to recycling technologies, particularly for carbon-based materials, is important. Considering these factors enables materials developers to minimise environmental impact and reduce dependency on scarce or geopolitically sensitive elements.

The introduction (Section 6.1.) is well-written, and provides a sensible definition of advanced materials. While the chapter emphasises fundamental research, it is worth noting that a clear boundary between fundamental and applied research does not always exist. Resolving the valley of death, the phase between early phase or fundamental research and commercialisation, is an important issue for European research policy. On the other hand, transfer and scale-up of advanced materials are crucial to bridge the gap between lab-scale innovation and industrial application. Research ecosystems that enable consistent performance, cost-efficiency, and integration into existing manufacturing systems make materials viable for commercial use, so that the citizen can benefit from tax money invested in fundamental research.

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Section 6.2. on advanced materials from biological systems is overall a nicely written chapter on biological materials. First, it could also include biodegradable materials in addition to bio-derived materials. While the main focus of the section is carbon-based materials, technologies that develop hybrid or even inorganic materials using biological systems can be mentioned. Second, current challenges associated with energy-intensive separation technologies need to be addressed. The lack of energy-efficient separation often prevents transfer and commercialisation in bio-technological processes. Fundamental research can help develop biological systems under conditions for a more cost-effective separation, making materials more viable for commercialisation. Third, the chapter can further explore the potential of biotechnology, such as developing biopolymers not available in nature, with enhanced properties while remaining sustainable and degradable.

Section 6.3. on energy conversion and storage is well-written, but needs improvements in relation to criticality, recycling, and circularity. First, many materials that are covered here contain metals, and we might not be able to produce them sustainably in sufficient amounts in the not-so-distant future. Therefore, criticality and making real changes in recycling efforts to keep materials in the loop need to be included. Second, Europe must rely on safe energy generation, supply, storage, and conversion; this point is well reflected in the chapter. Finally, there is a link between energy and carbon-based materials. We will need alternative carbon sources for everyday products, such as carbon-containing polymers, even in a de-fossilised future. This aspect should be highlighted.

Some additional comments refer to the need to refine the chapter in how it positions certain material classes. The examples of concrete materials classes are less palatable. These materials can be used as an example of prospective materials classes, but in the technical world it is not the best material that wins, but the one targeting specific needs while being cheap, energy-efficient, and eco-friendly that edges past the competition in the market. Limiting the scope of the chapter is needed, naming these materials at most as examples, as there are many new material classes that are not as discussed as others. The discussant disagrees with how the report describes many materials classes. For example, high-entropy alloys or MXenes are presented as top-priority classes, but they have already been around for some time. Instead, the following criteria should be used: what is really required; what is the processing perspective; what is the complete material space; and how can we foster an environment in material sciences focused on applications-orientation. This is the strength of some Asian countries leading in fields such as microelectronics, because they are fully oriented versus applications. A last example relates to battery-materials. The report mentions that lightweight targets of car manufacturers were not fully met, but the speaker is not sure about this. The discussant's feeling is that criticality and sustainability in battery materials need to be addressed. Sodium-ion batteries are already incorporated in car fleets in Asia, a research field that is neglected in Europe.

Summary of comments by the second discussant

The chapter is unbalanced in terms of materials classes, and adding some missing examples is suggested:

- **Metamaterials:** Metamaterials are really not materials, they are actual structures, but they are included as materials in PE11 Materials Engineering list. Adding details about metamaterials and their 3D structures to guide the properties of any materials, including advanced materials, would be useful.
- **Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs)(fibre-reinforced ceramics):** Ceramic materials, especially those that can be used at high temperature in highly demanding applications, such as energy and defence. Defence is not mentioned much in the report; however, defence research often benefits society.
- **High entropy ceramics (oxides and non-oxides):** They can have energy-related applications. They offer additional properties over conventional and even advanced ceramics.
- **Functional ceramics:** Europe still permits the use of lead-containing piezoelectric materials because it is difficult to find lead-free piezoelectric materials with similar properties. More research in this field is warranted.
- **Materials for high-temperature applications:** High-entropy ceramics and ultra-high temperature ceramics (UHTCs), can be expanded.

Further, the report focuses on the manufacturing *of* advanced materials but disregards the issue of manufacturing *with* advanced materials. For example, UHTCs require very specific and energy-intensive shaping and consolidation processes that could be improved with further research. There are, for instance, novel technologies in high-temperature sintering and shaping/forming of parts that could be exploited and promoted at a European level to foster the transition from laboratory to industry in advanced manufacturing. In addition to UHTCs, CMCs could also be mentioned as another relevant example.

Discussion

The co-chairs agreed with the comments and appreciated the list of missing elements. They described the rationale for dedicating a chapter to basic research. The ERC funds curiosity-driven research; the chapter showcases how EU projects bring innovation and disruption. The chapter also reports on EU flagship projects, many of which are applied research projects. The co-chairs agree to create a case studies section and add new examples beyond bio-based materials, including high-temperature materials and others suggested by the reviewers. They also agreed that, for e.g., in the 2D materials section there was too much of Mxene, which the group is not sure is an absolutely strategic material, but there is evidence on this for 2D materials in general.

The keynote speaker emphasised the importance of adding more data related to plastic waste and discussing the need and feasibility of biodegradability. On the second point related to biodegradability, the first discussant elaborates on how carbon sources and energy need to be kept in circulation. For

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example, the chemical industry uses fossil sources to make critical materials, such as lightweight materials and plastic, which are necessary for daily activities. While Europe heavily invests in recycling cascades and biodegradability is important, other sources of carbon are still needed.

The co-chair requested clarification on what biopolymer materials not seen in nature mean. The second discussant provided an example of cellulose with different crystalline properties, which can be synthesised using biotechnology, making the molecule better for specific applications. These materials have no relation to anything produced by an organism. Such ideas can trigger innovation.

A working group member suggested better describing and distinguishing between bio-based materials and biotechnology. Bio-based materials concern technologies that do not require biotechnology. For example, extracting biomass from cellulose is bio-based. On the other hand, biotechnology allows synthesis and design capabilities, creating novel polymers not found in nature.

Another working group member questioned whether it would be better to focus on classes of materials and their functionalities and applications rather than highlighting individual materials. The second discussant suggested discussing materials that fulfil the goals for specific applications. The chapter also needs to define applications that reach a certain performance, and therefore become a solution.

An invited discussant stressed that there is no conflict between fundamental research and innovation, and, on a second point, that inorganic materials should also be highlighted; if we are looking at the Europe's competitiveness, the main materials classes should be represented.

To conclude, a discussant argued that the advanced materials field is tomorrow's field, whereas the report largely discusses the advanced materials in the next 10 years. The goal should be to specify the requirements for what is needed and invent materials. He questions why the report did not follow this path.

The chair of the meeting concluded by agreeing with the second discussant on the importance of the process, not discussed enough in the report.

Summary of recommendations

First discussant

- General remarks:
 - ▶ Emphasise process development as part of advanced materials innovation to ensure scalability, reliability, and competitiveness; integrate it early to accelerate time-to-market and reduce risks.
 - ▶ Address sustainability and criticality in advanced materials development, including openness to recycling technologies for carbon-based materials.
- In the introduction (Section 6.1.), tackle the valley of death between fundamental research and commercialisation; highlight transfer and scale-up to bridge lab-scale innovation and industrial application.

- In biological materials (Section 6.2.), include biodegradable materials, hybrid/inorganic options, and address energy-intensive separation challenges; explore biotechnology for sustainable, degradable biopolymers with enhanced properties.
- In energy conversion and storage (Section 6.3.), add criticality and recycling for metals and highlight alternative carbon sources for polymers in a de-fossilised future.
- Additional comment: Refine how the chapter positions certain material classes: limit scope, apply clear prioritisation criteria, and address sustainability in battery materials; mention sodium-ion batteries as an emerging field.

Second discussant

- Balance materials classes by adding missing examples: metamaterials, ceramic matrix composites, high-entropy ceramics, functional ceramics, and materials for high-temperature applications (including UHTCs).
- Expand discussion on manufacturing: Address not only manufacturing *of* advanced materials but also manufacturing *with* them, noting the specific and energy-intensive processes required for UHTCs.

Review of Chapter 7: Conclusions; policy options and suggestions for the European leadership

Chapter overview

This is the most important chapter of the report, but it was considered incomplete and lacking concrete ideas. Several points were made regarding this chapter. First, most advanced materials are already governed by general product safety frameworks or policies for other materials, so there is a limited need to develop new policies. The report emphasises the importance of evidence-based regulation rather than over-regulation.

A working group member argued, however, that there is no evidence for over-regulation. Three examples are provided by the co-chair illustrating how over-regulation stifles innovation. The first one regards nanomaterials. All particles smaller than one hundred nanometres are considered the same in the regulatory agenda. Atomically, nanoparticles are often toxic for medical applications because they agglomerate. However, nanoparticles called clusters do not agglomerate and have tremendous implications in healthcare. Nevertheless, they are banned in Europe because of regulatory reasons, but not in the US and Japan. The second example was that thousands of fluorinated chemicals are grouped as one. Only a handful of those carrying long-chain hydro fluorinations, often called eternal chemicals, accumulate in the environment, whereas the rest of them do not. The same regulation applies to all of them, impeding their application in new technologies. As a final example, if any biological material, such as a protein or cellulose, is created in a single chemical reaction, the new regulations consider it unsustainable. This can prevent translation of bio-derived materials.

A second point from this chapter refers to how basic research is considered to be at the heart of enabling social transformation, that is, fundamental research is needed at all stages of innovation. For example, when transistors were discovered, they did not receive much attention and were sold for one dollar. This was partly because of the availability of vacuum tubes. Now transistors are everywhere because of this basic research discovery. Europe has strengths in research excellence, but there is a problem when translating it into technologies. Europe has also very good research infrastructure, and is strong in the aerospace, automotive, energy, electronics, and healthcare sectors.

Europe's weakness lies in regional problems, where different countries have different legislation and viewpoints. Scaling challenges across boundaries are present as well. For example, policy options are suggested for raw materials dependencies, but there is tremendous opposition to mining. There are also funding challenges; ways to solve them can be provided. Europe has a shortage of skilled equipment manufacturers and experts. It is challenging to retain them in Europe due to the competitive standards offered by China. Finally, there is also a discussion on the military as a first buyer of advanced materials. Whether Europe should use the geopolitical situation to create advanced materials, lightweight construction, and sensors to make robots and drones, is also questioned.

Summary of comments by the first discussant

The discussant provided comments related to improving policy options.

Policy options for sustainability

This section focuses on how to make materials more sustainable. There should be a balance between over-regulation and sustainability, as illustrated by the examples of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and fluorinated molecules. The report rightfully emphasises the use of digital solutions, especially in what regards provenance. For example, in Canada, when items are ordered from China, there is no information available on what metal or plastic the item is made of. Europe can establish its strength in digital provenance by creating watermarking of materials for import and export. This will improve recycling efforts and the circular economy.

Second, the recommendation about creating flexible, scalable, and adaptable manufacturing systems is sound. A key question is how to make the unit operations in production facilities more flexible. AI for chemical and materials engineering can certainly help reconfigure materials discovery and production workflows.

There should be a fine balance between regulation and innovation in Europe. Bringing life cycle aspects to the early stages of the discovery cycle could help with faster approvals. Mandating SSbD frameworks in materials innovation is critical. If researchers, industries, and academic consortia satisfy these requirements, the projects will move faster. Materials' design should be thought of as a racecar. The project should slow down only at specific objectives, such as environmental or biochemical damage; otherwise, it should accelerate. This art of accelerating and slowing down at the right places needs to be mastered in materials discovery.

Europe should spearhead the creation of a global database of input and output materials for all sectors. It would be beneficial to know which places sell waste to make a new material. Among all the larger economies, only the EU cares enough about sustainability to create digital solutions for the circular economy. Hence, having a digital presence in circular economy data would be crucial, and emphasising data in this section would be relevant.

Policy options for emerging technologies

Investing in digital twin, AI optimisation, and closed-loop systems is extremely important because they truly lead to accelerated materials discovery and commercialisation. In addition, R&D in emerging technologies should also focus on scale-up due to a huge gap between material discovery and scale-up. Europe already has places like Fraunhofer for this purpose.

Canada is already diversifying its economy and separating it from the US through the Buy Canada policy. Under this policy, the government must first procure a Canadian provider. This type of policy for green products is crucial for Europe. For example, Europe can prioritise green material purchase from member states rather than relying on cheap products from China. These efforts will also incentivise investment in

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the emerging technology, which is a challenge in Europe, lacking the level of venture capital available in North America. Incentivising mechanisms that create agile venture capital funds focused on advanced materials in Europe will be advantageous.

Policy options for advancing fundamental research

Some places in Europe use digital manufacturing and planned prototypes. For example, scientists at the University of Erlangen perform research on small molecule synthesis while also using formulation, deposition, and pilot plants to produce them. This needs to be encouraged. Research centres and initiatives can focus on how materials are integrated into a production line. Europe can establish such small pilot plants and reactors everywhere. In the end, scientists can think beyond just the fundamental materials discovery, and policymakers can invest in local testing sites for new materials, flow batteries, and other products.

The report discusses materials replacement to alleviate supply chain issues, but this should be emphasised in the context of fundamental research.

Summary of comments by the second discussant

Three main recommendations were offered to improve the report and the last chapter. The report should directly address the two scoping questions on European strategic autonomy and cross-fertilisation of innovation in advanced materials. The last chapter was considered somehow immature and artificial, if not read in the context of the entire report. It was challenging to identify how and where in the chapters these key questions were addressed. This could be outlined early in the report or at the beginning of each chapter and clearly stated. Chapter 2 on sustainability clearly addresses part “b” of the first scoping question regarding strategic autonomy, related to safe and sustainable advanced materials for the circular economy. However, where the EU’s core strength is, especially in regards to part a of the question, is unclear. More direct answers to these questions would increase the impact of the report.

The report needs revisions to ensure that the conclusions in Chapter 7 are supported by the main text and the rest of the chapters. For example, policy options for fundamental research provided in Section 7.1.3. are not sufficiently supported by Chapter 6. There is no sufficient link between the ideas in Chapters 6 and 7. It is also not clear whether the fundamental research areas in Chapter 6 were chosen based on the strength of European basic research or the potential for cross-fertilisation and innovation in advanced materials.

Finally, fundamental research on the manufacturing and processing of advanced materials is under-communicated in the report. There seems to be an artificial separation or distinction between fundamental research and materials manufacturing and processing of advanced materials. However, they are strongly connected. For example, the performance of a solar cell does not only depend on one single material, but it also depends on the way they work together. Therefore, fundamental research in advanced materials also includes the underlying science for materials fabrication and processing, it is

not just about the functional properties of the advanced materials. This is key to facilitating alignment and feedback loops between basic research and industrial needs.

Two final comments were made. First, advanced materials are often applied in combination with other advanced materials. Two examples are solar cells and batteries. This means that, to recirculate advanced materials, recycling strategies need to be on the key device design criteria, and not only on the device material. This is presented in the report, but could be further emphasised. This does not need to be a disadvantage; instead, it could be a competitive edge in the long-term perspective. Second, the report gives considerable attention to advanced materials from biological systems; however, the motivation for doing so is not clear and needs explaining.

Discussion

One of the invited discussants agrees that regulations are disadvantageous for the realisation and commercialisation of advanced materials in Europe. Another discussant points out that the current European regulation schemes evidently place a commercial burden on entities to bring materials up to scale, which is the highest among all the economic zones at the global scale. It will be important to establish an acceptable level of bureaucracy that can improve innovation and novel developments. If it is up to the international level and can still be dealt with, it will create a level playing field for Europe with other economic regions.

A discussant provided more context on regulation versus over-regulation. Regulation almost always comes into play later, when there is enough evidence on health and environmental risks. Most substances or groups of substances are banned as a precautionary measure. Communication and raising awareness are important aspects of avoiding over-regulation or broader restrictions.

A working group member considers the distinction between regulation and over-regulation to be a false dichotomy. The problem is of a more complex nature than regulation and over-regulation. First, a different model of innovation relies less on regulation than in embedding questions of safety and environmental risk from an early stage. Second, the problem with much regulation is that it is not carefully implemented. The current bureaucratic apparatus and the lack of public laboratories that can carefully think through the problem, make it challenging to solve problems related to regulation. Moreover, the US and China should not be models for regulation in Europe, because environmental disasters cause huge problems in those areas.

Summary of recommendations

First discussant

- Ensure the report addresses the two main questions in the scoping paper: 1) EU strategic autonomy, and 2) cross-fertilisation and innovation in advanced materials.
- Ensure that the conclusion given in the report (Chapter 7) is supported and reflected by the main text and chapters in the report.
- Fundamental research on manufacturing and processing of advanced materials is under-communicated in the report.
- Emphasise further that advanced materials are often applied in combination with other advanced materials.
- Review the considerable attention given to advanced materials from biological systems in the report.
- Policy options for sustainability:
 - ▶ Emphasise the importance of having a fine balance between over-regulation and sustainability; in the context of the discussion on digital provenance, the report could further highlight opportunities like watermarking materials for imports and exports to improve recycling and circular economy outcomes.
 - ▶ Creating flexible, scalable, and adaptable manufacturing systems is rightly recommended, but the report could emphasise the role of AI in reconfiguring materials discovery and production workflows.
 - ▶ Address the importance of a fine balance between regulation and innovation, bringing life cycle aspects to early stages, and mandating SSbD frameworks.
 - ▶ Emphasise data and a digital presence in circular economy efforts, highlighting Europe's role in establishing a global database of input and output materials.
- Policy options for emerging technologies:
 - ▶ Focus investment on digital twins, AI optimisation, and closed-loop systems, as well as the importance of scale-up for R&D in emerging technologies.
 - ▶ Emphasise the importance of prioritising green material procurement within Europe to encourage investment and reduce reliance on imports.
- Policy options for advancing fundamental research:
 - ▶ Encourage digital manufacturing and planned prototypes to better link materials discovery with production and scale-up.
 - ▶ Emphasise the importance of materials replacement to alleviate supply chain issues specifically in the context of fundamental research.

Closing remarks and next steps

The chair of the meeting thanked the working group for their efforts, and the invited experts for the contributions made and for their time. The comments were considered insightful and will have a positive impact in the report.

The co-chairs further thanked all participants and ensured that the inputs would be considered, while acknowledging the limitations in addressing some of the questions within the scope of the ERR. They also emphasised how much they learned with the comments, noting that European specificities still need to be highlighted.

The SAM Secretariat representative thanked all participants as well, emphasising the constructive feedback by all experts on the report.

Annexes

Annex 1: List of attendees

Invited experts

- **Alán Aspuru-Guzik**, University of Toronto, Canada
- **Paolo Colombo**, University of Padua, Italy
- **Liz Fisher**, University of Oxford, UK
- **Tor Grande**, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway
- **Oliver Hasse**, INAM – The Innovation Network for Advanced Materials, Germany
- **Alain Jonas**, Université Catholique de Louvain, WEL Research Institute, Belgium
- **Sir David King**, University of Cambridge, Climate Crisis Advisory Group, UK
- **Penny Nymark**, Karolinska Institute, Sweden
- **David Peck**, Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), Netherlands; Estonian Business School, Estonia
- **Sascha Sadewasser**, International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory (INL), Portugal
- **Stephan Andreas Schunk**, hte GmbH & BASF SE, Germany
- **Tejs Vegge**, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark
- **Polina Yaseneva**, University of Cambridge, UK

Working group members in attendance

- **Olli Ikkala**, Aalto University, Finland (co-chair of the WG)
- **Anke Weidenkaff**, TU Darmstadt, Germany (co-chair of the WG)
- **Norbert Babcsán**, Innobay Hungary Ltd., Hungary (chapter co-lead)
- **Andrew Barry**, University College London, UK
- **Anda Gromova**, Riga Technical University, Latvia
- **Steffen Hansen**, Technical University of Denmark, Denmark (chapter lead)
- **Astrid Lassen**, Aalborg University, Denmark
- **Rodrigo Martins**, NOVA University of Lisbon, Portugal (chapter co-lead)
- **Nicola Marzari**, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Switzerland; University of Cambridge, UK (chapter co-lead)
- **Risto Nieminen**, Aalto University, Finland (chapter lead)
- **Merja Penttilä**, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Finland

- **Laura Rodriguez-Lorenzo**, International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory (INL), Portugal (chapter lead)
- **Sabrina Sartori**, University of Oslo, Norway
- **Wei Sha**, Queen's University Belfast, UK
- **José Manuel Torralba**, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, IMDEA Materials Institute, Spain (chapter lead)
- **Luca Valentini**, University of Padua, Italy (chapter co-lead)

Members and alumni of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (observers)

- **Dimitra Simeonidou**
- **Nicole Grobert** (Alumni)

DG RTD, European Commission

- **Ingrid Zegers**, Team Leader (SAM)
- **Annabelle Ascher**, Secretary of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (SAM)
- **Geoffroy Delamare**, Policy Officer (SAM)
- **Jonathan Murphy**, Policy Officer (SAM)
- **Tina Zuechner**, Seconded National Expert

SAPEA staff

- **Mariana Rei**, Lead Scientific Policy Officer, Euro-CASE
- **Guna Dauvarte**, Scientific Policy Officer, FEAM
- **Louise Edwards**, Scientific Policy Officer, Academia Europaea/Cardiff University
- **Carly Seedall**, Scientific Policy Officer, Academia Europaea
- **Justine Moynat**, Communications Manager
- **Lionel Dutrieux**, Digital Communications Officer
- **Rudolf Hielscher**, Manager

Euro-CASE

- **Patrick Maestro**, Secretary-General
- **Nadia Pipunic**, Executive Assistant

Science Writer

- **Sejal Davla**

Annex 2: Programme

- 13:00-13:05** **Welcome and introduction to SAPEA**
Patrick Maestro (Secretary-General of Euro-CASE) – *In person*
- 13:05-13:15** **Introduction to the SAM and GCSA, and background to the request**
Geoffroy Delamare (EC SAM Secretariat) – *In person*
- 13:15-13:25** **Overview of the SAPEA evidence review report “advanced materials”**
Anke Weidenkaff, Olli Ikkala (Co-chairs of the working group) – *In person*
- 13:25-13:45** **Keynote:** Overview of the SAPEA evidence review report, with observations on strengths, possible limitations, and gaps
Alain Jonas, Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium (15 min) – *In person*
Discussion (5 min)
- 13:45-14:20** **Chapter 5: Policy, legislation, and governance of innovation ecosystems**
Overview of Chapter 5: Steffen Foss Hansen (5 min) - *Remotely*
Response by:
Penny Nymark, Karolinska Institute, Sweden (10 min) - *Remotely*
Liz Fisher, University of Oxford, UK (10 min) – *Remotely (first part)*
Discussion (10 min)
- 14:20-14:55** **Chapter 6: Basic research directions for future transition**
Overview of Chapter 6: Laura Rodriguez-Lorenzo (5 min) – *In person*
Responses by:
Stephan Andreas Schunk, hte GmbH & BASF SE, Germany (10 min) – *Remotely*
Paolo Colombo, University of Padova, Italy (10 min) - *Remotely*
Discussion (10 min)
- 14:55-15:30** **Coffee break**
- 15:30-16:05** **Chapter 3: Digitalisation: Data, simulations, and AI**
Overview of Chapter 3: Nicola Marzari (5 min) – *Remotely*
Responses by:
Tejs Vegge, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark (10 min) - *Remotely*
Oliver Hasse, INAM – The Innovation Network for Advanced Materials, Germany (10 min) - *Remotely*
Discussion (10 min)
- 16:05-16:40** **Chapter 4: Emerging technologies in manufacturing, scaling, and infrastructure**
Overview of Chapter 4: José Manuel Torralba (5 min) - *In person*
Responses by:
Polina Yaseneva, University College of London, UK (10 min) – *In person*
David Peck, Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), Netherlands (10 min) – *In person*
Discussion (10 min)

16:40-17:15	Chapter 2: A primer on sustainability: Concepts, processes, and best practices Overview of Chapter 2: Luca Valentini (5 min) – <i>In person (later)</i> Response by: Sir David King, University of Cambridge; Climate Crisis Advisory Group (CCAG), UK (10 min) - <i>Remotely</i> Sascha Sadewasser, International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, Portugal (10 min) – <i>In person</i> Discussion (10 min)
17:15-17:50	Chapter 7: Conclusions, policy options and suggestions for the European leadership Overview of Chapter 7: Anke Weidenkaff, Olli Ikkala (5 min) – <i>In person</i> Response by: Tor Grande, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway (10 min) – <i>In person</i> Alán Aspuru-Guzik, University of Toronto, Canada (10 min) – <i>Remotely (last hour)</i> Discussion (10 min)
17:50-18:00	Closing remarks and next steps Anke Weidenkaff and Olli Ikkala (Co-Chairs of the WG), Geoffroy Delamare (EC SAM Secretariat), Patrick Maestro (Euro-CASE) – <i>In person</i>
18:00	Closing of the meeting

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